

Conceptual framework for Teacher Educators' Diversity-Responsive Practices

Teacher educators hold a unique position in shaping future teachers' capacity to approach diversity in education. By influencing how future teachers think, teach, and model inclusivity, they play a pivotal role in reducing systemic inequalities within educational settings. Recognizing this potential, the *Teacher Educators' Diversity-Responsive Practices* (TE-DIP)¹ framework synthesizes research on practices that promote diversity-responsive education². This framework is a tool for guiding teacher educators and teams³ in their professional development and practices, emphasizing inclusion, equity, and social justice across teaching contexts, personal reflection, and societal engagement.

InFo-TED, ED-TED AND TEACHER EDUCATORS'

The framework subscribes to some basic assumptions about the nature of teacher educators' professionalism and teacher educator research that are shared by the InFo-TED network and the ED-TED Erasmus plus project (e.g. Vanderlinde, e.a., 2021). First, teacher educators are a very heterogeneous group of professionals representing different working contexts, responsibilities, backgrounds, experiences, etc.⁴ Second, teacher educators are strongly acknowledged as professionals who have good reasons for setting up their practices as they do. These practices are not merely observable actions but are grounded in teacher educators' knowledge, beliefs, and skills. This implies a positive appreciation of the activities, tasks, or practices teacher educators are already executing. Consequently, these practices

¹ In the article Ponet et al. (2025) the methodology is described of the systematic literature review that led to this framework. See: Ponet, B., Vantieghem, W., Tack, H., & Vanderlinde, R. (2025). Teacher educators' distinctive contribution to education that serves all: introducing a conceptual framework based on a systematic literature review. *European Journal of Teacher Education*, 1-21, <https://doi.org/10.1080/02619768.2025.2502393>

² The concept of diversity-responsive education is chosen here (see also Ponet, 2024) to recognize an educational system that not only embraces all forms of human diversity but genuinely serves every student, regardless of identity markers and the societal valuations ascribed to it. As such, diversity-responsive education, calls for ways of approaching diversity that promote inclusion, equity, and social justice.

³ The model was developed based on literature focusing primarily on individual teacher educators. However, its impact and relevance also extend to the team level, as the framework collectively encourages shared reflection, dialogue, and mutual learning, enabling teams to identify common challenges, align their approaches, and build a coherent vision of diversity-responsive teacher education.

⁴ While the ED-TED project subscribes to this broadened conceptualization, the project itself primarily concentrates on college-based teacher educators, and the examples provided (both in the accompanying text and in the resource bank) are predominantly directed towards this group of teacher educators.

are seen as the units of analysis for research on their professional development. Third, teacher educators are perceived as a unique and distinctive role of responsibility because they engage in permanent modelling when they teach. Not just what they teach, but also how they teach, is informative to the student teachers. This second-order pedagogy ensures that teacher educator practices always convey implicit professional messages. Fourth, the practices teacher educators implement are always situated. Both personal and contextual factors should be taken into account to understand the limitations and possibilities of what an individual teacher educator can do. For example, personal beliefs might determine what practices teacher educators are willing to set up spontaneously. The political context of a country or the policy of educational institutions, on the other hand, might determine what practices teacher educators are required or rather not allowed to implement. Furthermore, one's own positionality and thus experiences of privilege and oppression might influence what practices someone deems more important, especially in matters of diversity and (in)equity. Lastly, the framework takes into account underlying stances of teacher educators like empathy, critical reflection, openness, and self-awareness.

THE TE-DIP FRAMEWORK: AN OVERVIEW

The Teacher Educators' Diversity-Responsive Practices (TE-DIP) framework identifies six clusters of practices that teacher educators can implement to promote diversity-responsive education. The concept of diversity-responsive education is intrinsically linked to the purpose of reducing inequality, and is conceptualised in a twofold way: it is taking into account differences between people in order to create qualitative learning environments for all, as well as responding to discriminatory injustices that exist in society and (in)directly impact education, in order to create a more equitable world. The identified six clusters⁵ are supported by examples of concrete strategies and their application, and linked with examples or illustrations published on the ED-TED resource bank⁶. Additionally, the framework separates three contexts in which teacher educators engage in diversity-responsive practices: the first four clusters take place within their teaching roles, the fifth is implemented

⁵ The cluster creating safe learning environments is a precondition to the clusters creating inclusive learning environments and challenging student teachers' frames of reference, and is therefore visualised with an * in the model.

⁶ The ED-TED resource bank can be found via <https://info-ted.eu/resources/>.

in their professional development, and the last cluster in their responsibility as social change agents.

Figure 1: TE-DIP framework

1. Challenging Student Teachers' Frames of Reference

Prior research has demonstrated that how educational professionals think about their students and education in general can have an impact on student learning outcomes. As such, it is critical to address the frames of reference that shape one's thinking. In this context, a frame of reference refers to the set of beliefs, assumptions, values, and cultural perspectives through which student teachers interpret the world and their students. It shapes how they understand diversity, teaching, and learning, often unconsciously influencing their attitudes and actions in the classroom. To put it differently, these frames of reference can be about student teachers' direct beliefs on diversity and difference, as well as on their biases, privileges, self-perceptions, and cultural ways of understanding the world. The latter must be examined critically as well, because oppressive structures that disadvantage specific learners are often reproduced by subtle unintended remarks or actions. To equip future teachers with the tools to address systemic inequality, teacher educators must help them critically examine their beliefs, biases, and assumptions. This process involves deliberate activities designed to challenge entrenched worldviews.

Examples of practices:

- **Reflective journaling:** Ask student teachers to reflect on their cultural assumptions and privileges by writing weekly journals. For instance, a prompt might be, “*Describe a moment in your life when you experienced or observed an inequity. How did it shape your beliefs about teaching?*”
- **Role-playing exercises:** Facilitate scenarios where student teachers assume different roles, such as a student from a marginalized community, to foster empathy and awareness.
- **Critical texts and discussion:** Introduce literature like *Pedagogy of the Oppressed* by Paulo Freire to provoke critical dialogues about power dynamics in education.
- **Pedagogy of discomfort:** Use activities that create tension, such as debates about controversial topics, to push student teachers to confront their biases and reflect on alternate perspectives.

2. Creating Safe Learning Environments

A foundation for diversity-responsive practices is the establishment of a safe and supportive learning environment. When student teachers feel secure, they are more likely to engage openly in challenging conversations and reflective activities. Safety is a prerequisite for engaging in other clusters like challenging frames of reference or creating inclusive environments. Practices that promote safety enhance student teachers’ willingness to take risks and engage meaningfully.

Examples of practices:

- **Building trust:** Foster strong relationships with student teachers by actively listening to their concerns and showing empathy. For example, hold one-on-one check-ins to understand their needs and experiences.
- **Establishing norms for dialogue:** Co-create guidelines for respectful communication in the classroom, such as valuing all perspectives and allowing space for disagreement without hostility.

- **Demonstrating vulnerability:** Model openness by sharing your own challenges and learning experiences related to diversity, showing that everyone is on a journey of growth.
- **Power sharing:** Involve students in decision-making, such as allowing them to co-design class activities or select discussion topics, fostering a sense of ownership and equity.

Figure 2: Result of a search in the ED-TED Resource Bank: available resources by country for the practice 'create safe learning environment'

3. Creating Inclusive Learning Environments

Practices teacher educators can implement to create inclusive environments are rather similar to practices for teaching staff at all levels of education that are proclaimed by inclusive education research. This is understood broadly as fostering effective learning for all students. However, when teacher educators set up inclusive practices, teacher educators tap into an extra instructional opportunity: they implicitly model for their student teachers what those students can do in their future classrooms. By modelling inclusive education, teacher educators ensure that all student teachers feel valued and they demonstrate strategies student teachers can use in their future classrooms.

Examples of practices:

- **Differentiated instruction:** Customize assignments to meet diverse student needs. For instance, allow student teachers to choose between written essays, multimedia presentations, or collaborative projects based on their strengths and preferences.
- **Facilitating dialogue:** Create a safe space for discussion by establishing norms for respectful communication and encouraging the sharing of personal experiences.
- **Cooperative learning activities:** Organize group tasks where diverse students collaborate on projects, emphasizing each member's unique contributions.
- **Personalized support:** Identify student teachers' learning preferences or challenges early on and adapt resources to meet these needs, ensuring equitable access to success.

4. Explicit Modelling of Diversity-Responsive Practices

Teacher educators serve as role models, demonstrating diversity-responsive practices in their pedagogy. Explicit modelling (Boyd, 2014) involves making their instructional choices transparent to student teachers, showing how theory translates into practice. Consequently, an explicit modelling practice requires the implementation of practices that challenge student teachers' frames of reference (cluster 1), create safe learning environments (cluster 2) or to create inclusive learning environments (cluster 3).

Examples of practices:

- **Explaining pedagogical decisions:** During a lesson, a teacher educator might pause and say, *"I am using a cooperative learning strategy here to ensure everyone's voice is heard, which is a key principle of inclusive teaching."*
- **Thinking aloud:** Narrate decision-making processes during lessons, such as why certain materials were chosen to represent diverse perspectives.
- **Linking to theory:** Connect classroom practices to theories like *Culturally Responsive Pedagogy (CRP)*, explaining how they align with inclusive principles. For example, after using a case study about an immigrant student, discuss how CRP guides this choice.

- **Interactive debriefing:** Engage student teachers in reflective discussions about the inclusivity of modelled practices and brainstorm how they might apply similar strategies in their future classrooms.

5. Challenging One's Own Frames of Reference

Educational professionals deeply impact their students' outcomes by the way they think about matters of diversity and social inequality, as well as education at large (see cluster 1). This especially holds for teacher educators who must critically examine their own biases, assumptions, and practices to authentically model diversity-responsive teaching. This self-reflection helps them understand their positionality and adapt their approaches. This cluster emphasizes the importance of ongoing learning and vulnerability. By acknowledging and addressing their own limitations, teacher educators demonstrate authenticity and commitment to their student teachers.

Examples of practices:

- **Practitioner research:** Conduct self-studies to identify areas where personal biases may affect teaching. For example, a teacher educator might analyse their feedback on student work to ensure it is equitable across all cultural backgrounds.
- **Exploring positionality:** Engage in workshops or professional learning communities that explore privilege and identity, such as analysing Peggy McIntosh's concept of the "invisible knapsack."
- **Reflexive journaling:** Write reflections after each class session, focusing on moments of discomfort or bias and considering alternative approaches for future teaching.
- **Participating in professional development:** Attend sessions on diversity and inclusion topics, such as workshops on antiracist education, to stay informed and refine practices.

DISCO-instrument

In Flanders, a measurement and reflection tool called DISCO was developed to grasp teachers' beliefs and sense of efficacy towards diversity in education from an inclusive perspective. Rather than evaluating practical skills, it captures teachers' self-assessment of their beliefs and perceived competence, and it considers diverse learners as a whole rather than focusing on any specific group.

DISCO is a 20-minute questionnaire available in Dutch, French, and English. It can be used by both teacher educators and pre-service teachers **after registering**, either individually or as a group (with a group name), the latter allowing insight into the average results within a school team. The process is fully anonymous, and participants receive personal feedback after submission.

Reflecting on your beliefs as a (pre-service) teacher about student diversity and educational inclusion is crucial. Equally important is gaining insight into your sense of competence, efficacy, or self-efficacy in creating inclusive learning environments. While positive beliefs about diversity are essential for viewing it as an asset rather than a barrier to learning, a teacher's sense of efficacy is central to their motivation and actual classroom performance.

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Access to the resource: [DISCO-instrument](#)

Audio description

Figure 3: Result of a search within the practice 'Challenging One's Own Frames of Reference': a measurement and reflection tool for dealing with diversity

6. Raising Societal Responsiveness to Diversity

Beyond their teaching assignment and their own professional development, teacher educators can influence systemic change by advocating for equity and inclusion within their institutions and society at large. Teacher educators' advocacy roles extend their influence, positioning them as vital contributors to a more equitable educational landscape.

Examples of practices:

- **Curriculum Review:** Collaborate with colleagues to evaluate teacher education programmes for biases or gaps. For example, audit syllabi to ensure diverse perspectives are represented.
- **Public advocacy:** Participate in policy discussions or publish articles advocating for inclusive education reforms, amplifying the voice of teacher educators as agents of change.
- **Community engagement:** Partner with local organizations to address educational inequities, such as mentoring programs for underrepresented students pursuing teaching careers.

- **Conducting collaborative research:** Work with schools to study the impact of diversity-focused interventions, contributing evidence to support systemic changes in education policy and practice.

Perspectives of the Finnish School for All – Inclusiveness, diversity and equity?

In this podcast four Finnish researchers discuss various aspects of the Finnish education system. First, the background and the basic principles of the Finnish school for all are introduced. After that an inclusive school in practice is presented. Next inclusiveness is discussed from the viewpoint of special education and finally Finnish school system is considered from the point of view of cultural and worldview diversity. The discussion includes also critical aspects of the system, as well as reflections on how to better educate future teachers in our teacher education programs.

Interviewer: Dr Sonja Laine, University of Helsinki

Interviewees: Dr Anna-Leena Riitaola, University of Helsinki, Dr Anni Loukomies, University of Helsinki, Dr Juho Honkasilta, University of Helsinki, Dr Inkeri Rissanen, University of Tampere

Read the entire podcast transcript here: [Perspectives of the Finnish School for All and further reading](#)

Figure 4: Result of a search within the practice 'Raising Societal Responsiveness to Diversity': a Finnish podcast in which researchers discuss inclusive education.

UNDERLYING COMPETENCIES

Based on the TE-DIP framework, teacher educators require a combination of knowledge, skills, and attitudes to engage successfully in diversity-responsive education. They need a deep understanding of processes of inclusion, equity, and social justice, as well as insight into how sociocultural and institutional contexts shape educational practices. Essential skills include facilitating critical reflection, creating safe and inclusive learning environments, modelling diversity-responsive pedagogy, and collaborating within teacher education teams to align approaches and foster coherence across programmes. These practices must be grounded in attitudes such as empathy, openness, critical self-awareness, and a strong commitment to equity and social justice. Ultimately, diversity-responsive teacher educators embody a reflexive professionalism, continuously learning, questioning their assumptions, and acting as change agents within and beyond their institutions.

PROFESSIONAL DEVELOPMENT AND COLLABORATIVE ENGAGEMENT WITHIN TEAMS

Developing the practices described in the TE-DIP framework requires intentional, sustained, and contextually embedded professional learning opportunities. Building on the foundations of InFo-TED and the ED-TED project, professional development should be conceived not merely as an individual endeavour but as a collaborative and systemic process situated within teacher education teams. At the meso-level of teacher education institutions, teams play a pivotal role in shaping program coherence, fostering a shared professional culture, and linking individual practices to institutional goals.

When used collectively, the TE-DIP framework offers a conceptual language and structure that support joint reflection, inquiry, and development among teacher educators. Through collaborative engagement - such as peer observation, shared analysis of practice, and joint curriculum design - teams can identify strengths and challenges in their diversity-responsive practices, explore how institutional conditions enable or constrain their work, and co-construct strategies for improvement. Such team-based professional learning fosters coherence across courses, enhances collective responsibility for diversity-responsive education, and nurtures a shared professional identity grounded in inclusion, equity, and social justice.

Moreover, collective use of the framework encourages teams to move beyond the aggregation of individual competencies toward a systemic culture of responsiveness and equity. Program leaders play a crucial role in facilitating this collaborative engagement by creating structural and cultural conditions - such as time, institutional support, and recognition - that enable teacher educators to engage meaningfully with the TE-DIP framework. In this way, the framework supports both individual and collective professional growth, strengthening the presence and sustainability of diversity-responsive practices within teacher education programmes.

SIGNIFICANCE OF THE FRAMEWORK

The TE-DIP has expanded the knowledge base on teacher educator practices to foster diversity-responsive education, that any teacher educator could implement. The introduction of a cohesive vocabulary provides a common language that allows professionals,

policymakers, teams, and researchers to engage in less ambiguous conversations with each other about ways teacher educators approach diversity that promote inclusion, equity, and social justice, and thus contributing to the reduction of systematic inequalities. As such, teacher educators are truly considered change agents. Particularly, the TE-DIP framework helps to discuss, evaluate, and inspire professional development of teacher educators' practices. However, the framework should not be regarded as a tool for individual reflection and practice only. Its full potential emerges when it is used collaboratively within teams of teacher educators. Applying the TE-DIP collectively encourages shared reflection, dialogue, and mutual learning, allowing teams to identify common challenges, align their approaches, and build a coherent vision on diversity-responsive teacher education. Such collective engagement strengthens consistency across courses and programs and fosters a supportive professional community in which teacher educators can model these practices together. As a result of well-designed professional development initiatives, teacher educators and teams of teacher educators can become better in modelling ideas of diversity-responsive education, improving the preparation of student teachers, and, eventually, impacting how diversity and social inequality are approached in the broader educational field.

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